

CASE REPORT

Esthetic rehabilitation of medially deviated anterior teeth through CAD/CAM fabrication zirconia crowns: A case report

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Abstract

This case report shows how the esthetic rehabilitation of medially deviated anterior dentition with the application of zirconia crowns. The rehabilitation process started with oral examination with an initial impression, then a smile design with gingivectomy to aid the crown lengthening. The following treatment-specific teeth were prepared with an impression to allow temporary restorations to be placed. The findings indicate that the specific material for restoration may have an effective role in the rehabilitation process.

Keywords biocompatible materials, crown, crown lengthening, dental impression, design equipment

1 | Introduction

In the anterior region of our oral cavity, aesthetics plays an important role along with function and space management, and achieving this can be challenging. Tooth rehabilitation in this region becomes fundamental. Misplaced midline causes an

asymmetry in the face that may not be aesthetically appealing. Misplaced midline happens when there is trauma, dental disease that can loosen the teeth causing it to move, and sometimes misplaced midline can be caused not because of malposition teeth but because the jaw itself is out of position. Due to the demand for

esthetic restorations, it has resulted in an increased use of dental ceramics for

mechanical and chemical properties suitable for medical application, biocompatibility and durability.

Figure 1. Diagnostic tools using (A) pre-treatment extraoral and (B) intraoral photographs

anterior and posterior restorations. According to studies, all-ceramic restorations were restricted in the anterior region, but now it can be made anywhere in the dentition.¹

Ceramic cannot withstand tensile forces as well as metal and they are susceptible to brittle fractures. A new type of ceramic material, based on zirconium oxide, has been developed more recently.² Zirconia was introduced into dentistry in the 1990s because of its good mechanical and chemical properties and is currently being used as a material for frameworks, dowels, implants, abutments and orthodontic brackets.³ It has both clinical popularity and success due to its outstanding

Because of its good success rate with minimal complications and its high fracture toughness, zirconia is becoming a prevalent biomaterial in dentistry. In this case report, the patient's concern was her dissatisfaction with the appearance of her maxillary anterior teeth and she opted to replace the tooth crown with Zirconia due to more advantages.

2 | Case presentation section

2.1. Chief complaint

A 23-year-old female patient came to the clinic for dental treatment. Her primary concern was her dissatisfaction with the appearance of

her maxillary anterior teeth. The patient reported night bruxism and occasionally tooth clenching during the day. She was in good health, and the medical history showed no significant abnormality.

Oral hygiene was fair and there was no periodontal problem (Figure 1).

Figure 2. (A) Digital smile design (B) Computer-aided crown design (C) Temporary crown fabrication and installment

2.2. Diagnosis & etiology

Clinical examination revealed that the patient had medially deviated teeth or misplaced midline. She underwent a composite restoration on her tooth number 46 and 27. She had a missing maxillary left central incisor that was treated with a composite crown placed on her left lateral incisor. She wanted to replace her tooth crown with a more aesthetically pleasing and natural looking restoration that will correct her

misaligned midline to feel at ease to smile and recover her self-confidence. After clinical examination, initial alginate impressions were taken and study casts were fabricated.

2.3. Treatment

The treatment of choice for this patient included Zirconia Crown Bridge for all maxillary anterior teeth. Porcelain crown was selected as a treatment option which was found cheapest and at the same time exhibits a natural look. Provided with disadvantages and advantages of both, the patient opted to have zirconia crowns.

First appointment, after oral examination, a digital smile design was made to envision the treatment outcome (Figure 2-A). Two days after, part of the planned treatment was to do gingivectomy to the patient for crown lengthening. This is to fully establish enough place to the crown. A prepared crown was designed digitally for all maxillary anterior teeth (Figure 2-B).

During the third appointment, soft tissue was completely healed after two weeks. Tooth preparation procedure was made for tooth numbers 13, 12, 11, 22, and 23. Followed by impression taking in preparation for fabrication of

temporary crown. Patient then was installed with a temporary crown which is shown in Figure 2-C.

After 3 weeks, Zirconia Crown Bridge was installed for the final treatment through cementation, using SA Cement Plus (Figure 3). Patient was educated on oral hygiene measures and maintenance for the restoration. Preoperative and post-operative photographs are shown in Figure 3.

crown that will correct the alignment of her teeth. Zirconia-based restorations were chosen due to the high fracture toughness of the ceramic framework in light of the patient's documented bruxism. This was selected for its esthetic characteristics, durability and biocompatibility. Additionally, it exhibits increased abrasion resistance, color and contour stability, appropriate translucency and excellent tissue response due to

Figure 3. (A) Preoperative and postoperative photograph (B) Installation of Zirconia crown bridge

3 | Discussion

This case report involved the esthetic rehabilitation for a 23-year-old female patient who complained about the midline misalignment of her teeth. She had a previous composite crown treatment on one tooth but she wanted to replace it with a bridge

minimal plaque accumulation.⁴ According to studies, zirconia crowns are a promising prosthodontic alternative to metal ones and exhibit good clinical performance based on observation and in vivo investigations.⁵

The selection of zirconia crown bridge was upon both clinical considerations and patient's preference. With the help of CAD/CAM

technique it designs and fabricates the anatomic full-contour zirconia crown with excellent marginal adaptation.⁶ Patient has short clinical crowns which commenced the initial treatment, the gingivectomy. This is to enable crown lengthening and the adjustment of the shape of the crown. With the advancement of Zirconia material, its biocompatibility is high promoting healthy tissue response which later succeeded the chosen treatment.⁷ In contrast with porcelain crown, zirconia lasts longer, withstands wear and tear without chipping which further tolerates forces of mastication and bruxism. In addition, it also imitates more naturally looking appearance that addresses the main concern of the patient.⁸ In this clinical report, a 6-unit zirconia crown bridge was installed in the maxillary anterior teeth of the patient, having restored the edentulous space on tooth 21 and the esthetic concern of the patient on the rest of the anterior teeth. During the 12-week follow up, results showed no significant problem with positive feedback from the patient.

According to Sola-Ruiz et al.,⁹ Results For the 50 monolithic zirconia crowns analyzed, the survival rate was 98% after 5 years. Only 6% of the crowns presented some type of complication (two debonding and one root fracture). No fracture or fissures were detected.

4 | Conclusions

A misplaced midline results in asymmetry in the face, which may not be aesthetically pleasing and in need for rehabilitation. The use of dental ceramics for anterior and posterior restorations has increased as a result of the desire for cosmetic restorations. However, ceramic is more prone to brittle fractures and cannot bear tensile stresses as well as metal. Based on zirconium oxide, this new kind of ceramic material has achieved clinical success and popularity thanks to its exceptional mechanical and chemical properties that make it acceptable for use in medicine. Regarding the case of the patient, Zirconia-based crown was chosen because of its remarkable strength and aesthetic attributes. It is superior than porcelain fused to metal as a treatment for it can survive wear and tear without chipping and can also withstand the stresses of bruxism and mastication.

Institutional Review Board Statement

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, and approved by the Ethics Committee of Southwestern University PHINMA School of dentistry.

Informed Consent Statement

Informed consent was obtained from the patient and the attending dentist.

All methods have been exhausted to maintain the anonymity of the patient.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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